

ANTI-PATTERNS CATALOG IN PYTHON

ANTI-PATTERN GENERAL DATA				
ID	TITLE			
P_V2	Use of reserved word for variable name			
EXAMPLE:				
<pre>def main(): int = int(input()) print(int) main()</pre>				
ERROR TYPE:	X	Syntax		Semantics
CONTENT:	- General: Identifier names			
IN WHAT LANGUAGE WAS THE MISTAKE MADE?		C	X	Python
PROBLEM:				
Reserved words such as "print," "int," "input," among others, cannot be used for identifiers, such as variable names.				
CONNECTIONS TO OTHER ANTI-PATTERNS:				
- V1 – Use of nonexistent variable				
- V3 – Assignment using “==” instead of “=”				
EVENTS				
Note: In the code snippets presented below, only the anti-pattern question of this table was analyzed. If other errors exist, these errors have been handled in other anti-patterns.				
EVENT 1				
Student Id: 3237		Total of submissions of the exercise:		2
The exercise that was being solved:				
Exercise 1.1				
<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre>int = int(input()) print(int)</pre> <p>Occurred in submission: 1 Observation: Used the reserved word “int” to name the variable.</p>		<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <pre>inteiro = int(input()) print(inteiro)</pre> <p>Fixed on submission: 2 Observation:</p>		
EVENT 2				
Student Id: 4730		Total of submissions of the exercise:		16
The exercise that was being solved:				
Exercise 1.1				

Error	Fixed Error
<pre>int = input("Digite um numero inteiro: ") print("O numero inteiro dado foi: ", int)</pre>	
<p>Occurred in submission: 1 Observation: Used the reserved word "int" to name the variable.</p>	<p>Fixed on submission: Observation: The error has not been fixed.</p>

EVENT 3		
Student Id: 3498	Total of submissions of the exercise:	9

The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 3.3

Error	Fixed Error
<pre>soma = int</pre>	
<p>Occurred in submission: 1 Observation: Instead of "int" should have a value or a variable.</p>	<p>Fixed on submission: Observation: The error has not been fixed.</p>

EVENT 4		
Student Id: 2068	Total of submissions of the exercise:	3

The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 7.2

Error	Fixed Error
<pre>pot = float</pre>	
<p>Occurred in submission: 2 Observation: Instead of "float" should have a value or a variable.</p>	<p>Fixed on submission: Observation: The error has not been fixed.</p>

A SUGGESTED SOLUTION		
FOR PROFESSORS		
Groups working with step-by-step execution to understand errors – reinforce with exercises		
FOR STUDENTS		
Study one or more anti-patterns, introduce to classmate and reinforce with exercise		

ANTI-PATTERN GENERAL DATA

ID	TITLE				
P_V4	Incorrect data type conversion				
EXAMPLE:					
<pre style="margin: 0;">def main(): x = int print(x) main()</pre>					
ERROR TYPE:					
	X	Syntax		Semantics	Style
CONTENT: - Variable: Type Conversion					
IN WHAT LANGUAGE WAS THE MISTAKE MADE?					
		C		X	Python
PROBLEM:					
The conversion syntax must be maintained for the compiler to understand, and Python type conversion is done by enclosing the type name followed by parentheses with the data to be converted. Ex .: int ("1234")					
CONNECTIONS TO OTHER ANTI-PATTERNS:					
- P_V5 – Missing type conversion					
EVENTS					
<p>Note: In the code snippets presented below, only the anti-pattern question of this table was analyzed. If other errors exist, these errors have been handled in other anti-patterns.</p>					
EVENT 1					
Student Id: 4762		Total of submissions of the exercise:			5
The exercise that was being solved:					
Exercise 1.1					
Error <pre style="margin: 0;">x = int</pre>			Fixed Error <pre style="margin: 0;">x = int(input("digite x:"))</pre>		
Occurred in submission: 1 Observation: There are missing the parentheses with the parameter of what will be converted, right after "int".			Fixed on submission) 5 Observation:		
EVENT 2					
Student Id: 5594		Total of submissions of the exercise:			6
The exercise that was being solved:					
Exercise 4.7					
Error <pre style="margin: 0;">num=input(int("num: "))</pre>			Fixed Error <pre style="margin: 0;">num=int(input())</pre>		

Occurred in submission: 1 Observation: The "int" and the "input" are in reverse order.	Fixed on submission: 4 Observation:
EVENT 3	
Student Id: 4842	Total of submissions of the exercise: 4
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 1.1	
Error <code>n=int.input ()</code>	Fixed Error <code>n=int (input ())</code>
Occurred in submission: 1 Observation: After this "int" must have parentheses.	Fixed on submission: 4 Observation:
EVENT 4	
Student Id:	Total of submissions of the exercise:
The exercise that was being solved:	
Error	Fixed Error
Occurred in submission: Observation:	Fixed on submission: Observation:
A SUGGESTED SOLUTION	
FOR PROFESSORS	
Groups working with step-by-step execution to understand errors – reinforce with exercises	
FOR STUDENTS	
Study one or more anti-patterns, introduce to classmate and reinforce with exercise	

ANTI-PATTERN GENERAL DATA

ID	TITLE
P_V5	Missing type conversion
EXAMPLE:	
<pre>n=input("Digite um numero natural: ")</pre>	
ERROR TYPE:	
	Syntax <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Semantics <input type="checkbox"/>
	Style <input type="checkbox"/>
CONTENT:	
- Variable: Type Conversion	
IN WHAT LANGUAGE WAS THE MISTAKE MADE?	
	C <input type="checkbox"/>
	Python <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
PROBLEM:	
Failure to convert, when necessary, will make the data not be in the proper format so that the program can work. This error will be noticed during program execution.	
CONNECTIONS TO OTHER ANTI-PATTERNS:	
- P_V4 – Incorrect data type conversion	
EVENTS	
Note: In the code snippets presented below, only the anti-pattern question of this table was analyzed. If other errors exist, these errors have been handled in other anti-patterns.	
EVENT 1	
Student Id: 5594	Total of submissions of the exercise: 6
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 4.7	
<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre>n=input("Digite um numero natural: ")</pre> <p>Occurred in submission: 1 Observation: The conversion of input data to numeric type is missing.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <pre>n=int(input())</pre> <p>Fixed on submission: 3 Observation:</p>
EVENT 2	
Student Id: 4730	Total of submissions of the exercise: 3
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 1.2	
<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre>num = input("Digite um numero inteiro: ")</pre> <p>Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <pre>n = input("Digite um numero inteiro: ") num = int(n)</pre> <p>Fixed on submission: 2 Observation:</p>
EVENT 3	
Student Id: 4762	Total of submissions of the exercise: 3

The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 1.2	
Error <pre>x = input("digite x:")</pre>	Fixed Error <pre>x = int(input("digite x:"))</pre>
Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:	Fixed on submission: 3 Observation:
EVENT 4	
Student Id: 4842	Total of submissions of the exercise: 3
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 2.1	
Error <pre>n=input ()</pre>	Fixed Error <pre>n=int (input ())</pre>
Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:	Fixed on submission: 2 Observation:
A SUGGESTED SOLUTION	
FOR PROFESSORS	
Programming in front of the students, making the error appear – reinforce by asking students to develop new codes	
FOR STUDENTS	
Study one or more anti-patterns, introduce to classmate and reinforce with exercise	

ANTI-PATTERN GENERAL DATA

ID	TITLE					
P_IF4	Missing parentheses in "input"					
EXAMPLE:						
<pre style="margin: 0;">a = input print (a)</pre>						
ERROR TYPE:						
	X	Syntax		Semantics		Style
CONTENT:						
- Data input function - Function						
IN WHAT LANGUAGE WAS THE MISTAKE MADE?						
		C		X	Python	
PROBLEM:						
Every function name is followed by parentheses used to put parameters, even if they do not exist. Since "input" is a function, it must be followed by parentheses.						
CONNECTIONS TO OTHER ANTI-PATTERNS:						
- P_IF4 - Missing quotes in the input function call						
EVENTS						
Note: In the code snippets presented below, only the anti-pattern question of this table was analyzed. If other errors exist, these errors have been handled in other anti-patterns.						
EVENT 1						
Student Id: 4746		Total of submissions of the exercise:		6		
The exercise that was being solved:						
Exercise 1.1						
Error <pre style="margin: 0;">a = input</pre>		Fixed Error <pre style="margin: 0;">a = input ()</pre>				
Occurred in submission: 1 Observation: Parentheses are missing right after "input."		Fixed on submission: 2 Observation:				
EVENT 2						
Student Id: 4690		Total of submissions of the exercise:		8		
The exercise that was being solved:						
Exercise 1.1						
Error <pre style="margin: 0;">n = int(input)</pre>		Fixed Error <pre style="margin: 0;">n = int(input(''))</pre>				
Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:		Fixed on submission: 5 Observation:				
EVENT 3						
Student Id: 4962		Total of submissions of the exercise:		4		

The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 1.1	
Error <code>a=int(input)</code>	Fixed Error <code>a=int(input())</code>
Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:	Fixed on submission: 3 Observation:
EVENT 4	
Student Id:	Total of submissions of the exercise:
The exercise that was being solved:	
Error	Fixed Error
Occurred in submission: Observation:	Fixed on submission: Observation:
A SUGGESTED SOLUTION	
FOR PROFESSORS	
Explanation using blackboard and projector – reinforce the concept using Kahoot	
FOR STUDENTS	
Solve exercises, add code errors, and ask classmate to find them	

ANTI-PATTERN GENERAL DATA

ID	TITLE				
P_OF5	"print" followed by "=" or other incorrect parameter				
EXAMPLE:					
<pre style="color: #000080;">print= ("n")</pre>					
ERROR TYPE:					
X	Syntax		Semantics		Style
CONTENT: - Data Output Function					
IN WHAT LANGUAGE WAS THE MISTAKE MADE?					
		C		X	Python
PROBLEM:					
The "=" sign is used for assignment and since "print" is not a variable, it cannot be followed by this sign.					
CONNECTIONS TO OTHER ANTI-PATTERNS:					
- P_OF2 – Missing quotation mark in output function - P_OF4 – Missing comma to separate parameters in data output function					
EVENTS					
Note: In the code snippets presented below, only the anti-pattern question of this table was analyzed. If other errors exist, these errors have been handled in other anti-patterns.					
EVENT 1					
Student Id: 4858		Total of submissions of the exercise:			2
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 1.1					
Error			Fixed Error		
<pre style="color: #000080;">n=int(input()) print= ("n")</pre>			<pre style="color: #000080;">n=int(input()) print (n)</pre>		
Occurred in submission: 1			Fixed on submission: 2		
Observation:			Observation:		
EVENT 2					
Student Id: 3498		Total of submissions of the exercise:			9
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 3.3					
Error			Fixed Error		
<pre style="color: #000080;">print '%d' %soma</pre>					
Occurred in submission: 1			Fixed on submission:		
Observation: The '%d' will be considered text, but the '%' in front of the variable "soma" is			Observation: The error has not been fixed.		

wrong because the student wanted to print the value stored in "soma".

EVENT 3

Student Id: 4698 Total of submissions of the exercise: 4

The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 1.2

Error

```
print = (a**2)
```

Occurred in submission: 1
Observation:

Fixed Error

```
print(a**2)
```

Fixed on submission: 4
Observation:

EVENT 4

Student Id: Total of submissions of the exercise:

The exercise that was being solved:

Error

Occurred in submission:
Observation:

Fixed Error

Fixed on submission:
Observation:

A SUGGESTED SOLUTION

FOR PROFESSORS

Explanation using blackboard and projector – reinforce the concept using Kahoot

FOR STUDENTS

Solve exercises, add code errors, and ask classmate to find them

ANTI-PATTERN GENERAL DATA

ID	TITLE				
P_AE2	Wrong arithmetic operator				
EXAMPLE:					
<pre style="color: #e67e22;">print (n^2)</pre>					
ERROR TYPE:					
X	Syntax		Semantics		Style
CONTENT:					
- Arithmetic Expression					
IN WHAT LANGUAGE WAS THE MISTAKE MADE?					
		C		X	Python
PROBLEM:					
Each operation has its own operator. Using a wrong operator may cause a syntax error as it does not exist within the Python language or, if it exists, will give a semantic error as it will not generate the expected result.					
CONNECTIONS TO OTHER ANTI-PATTERNS:					
EVENTS					
<p>Note: In the code snippets presented below, only the anti-pattern question of this table was analyzed. If other errors exist, these errors have been handled in other anti-patterns.</p>					
EVENT 1					
Student Id: 4858		Total of submissions of the exercise:			3
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 1.2					
Error <pre style="color: #e67e22;">print (n^2)</pre>			Fixed Error <pre style="color: #e67e22;">print (n**2)</pre>		
Occurred in submission: 1 Observation: Used operator “^” instead of “**.”			Fixed on submission: 2 Observation:		
EVENT 2					
Student Id: 4914		Total of submissions of the exercise:			2
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 1.2					
Error <pre style="color: #e67e22;">print (numero^2)</pre>			Fixed Error <pre style="color: #e67e22;">print (numero*numero)</pre>		
Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:			Fixed on submission: 2 Observation:		
EVENT 3					
Student Id: 5002		Total of submissions of the exercise:			2

The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 1.2	
Error <code>quad = n^2</code>	Fixed Error <code>quad = n**2</code>
Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:	Fixed on submission: 2 Observation:
EVENT 4	
Student Id: 4954	Total of submissions of the exercise: 2
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 1.2	
Error <code>print (n^n)</code>	Fixed Error <code>print (n*n)</code>
Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:	Fixed on submission: 2 Observation:
A SUGGESTED SOLUTION	
FOR PROFESSORS	
Groups working with step-by-step execution to understand errors – reinforce with exercises	
FOR STUDENTS	
Study one or more anti-patterns, introduce to classmate and reinforce with exercise	

ANTI-PATTERN GENERAL DATA

ID	TITLE			
P_SS1	Missing ":" at end of "if" or "else" line			
EXAMPLE:				
<pre style="font-family: monospace; color: #c00000;">if(a>b) ← print (a) else ← print (b)</pre>				
ERROR TYPE:				
X	Syntax		Semantics	Style
CONTENT: - Selection structure				
IN WHAT LANGUAGE WAS THE MISTAKE MADE?				
		C	X	Python
PROBLEM:				
Colon ":" indicates the beginning of a block, so after "if" and "else" it must be inserted in the code.				
CONNECTIONS TO OTHER ANTI-PATTERNS:				
- SS2 – Not using "else" where it would be appropriate to do so				
EVENTS				
Note: In the code snippets presented below, only the anti-pattern question of this table was analyzed. If other errors exist, these errors have been handled in other anti-patterns.				
EVENT 1				
Student Id: 2068		Total of submissions of the exercise:		3
The exercise that was being solved:				
Exercise 2.1				
Error		Fixed Error		
<pre style="font-family: monospace; color: #c00000;">if(a>b) print (a) else print (b)</pre>		<pre style="font-family: monospace; color: #c00000;">if a>b: print (a) else: print (b)</pre>		
Occurred in submission: 1		Fixed on submission: 3		
Observation: Missing ":" at the end of the "if" and "else" lines.		Observation:		
EVENT 2				
Student Id: 2257		Total of submissions of the exercise:		10
The exercise that was being solved:				
Exercise 2.1				
Error		Fixed Error		

```

if a >= c
    print a
else
    print c

```

Occurred in submission: 1
Observation:

```

if a>=c:
    print a
else:
    print c

```

Fixed on submission: 2
Observation:

EVENT 3

Student Id: 4698 Total of submissions of the exercise: 5

The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 2.1

Error

```

if a>b
print(a)

```

Occurred in submission: 2
Observation:

Fixed Error

```

if a>b:
    print(a)

```

Fixed on submission: 4
Observation:

EVENT 4

Student Id: 4794 Total of submissions of the exercise: 3

The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 2.1

Error

```

if n > x
    print(n)

```

Occurred in submission: 1
Observation:

Fixed Error

```

if n > x:
    print(n)

```

Fixed on submission: 2
Observation:

**A SUGGESTED SOLUTION
FOR PROFESSORS**

Explanation using blackboard and projector – reinforce the concept using Kahoot
FOR STUDENTS

Solve exercises, add code errors, and ask classmate to find them

ANTI-PATTERN GENERAL DATA

ID	TITLE
P_RS1	Wrong sequence of commands in structure

EXAMPLE:

```
def main():
    n=int(input())
    i=1
    while i<=n:
        a=int(input())
        l=[]
        l.append(a)
        if a>0:
            l.append(0)
        i=i+1
    i=0
    L=[]
    while i<len(l):
        if l[i]!=0:
            a=l[i]%2
            if a!=0:
                L.append(a)
            i=i+1
    print L
else:
    print 0
main()
```

ERROR TYPE:	Syntax	X	Semantics		Style
CONTENT:	- Repetition structure: execution				
IN WHAT LANGUAGE WAS THE MISTAKE MADE?		C		X	Python

PROBLEM:

The order of the commands influences the result of the program, so it is essential to take care of the order stipulated for the commands used.

CONNECTIONS TO OTHER ANTI-PATTERNS:

EVENTS

Note: In the code snippets presented below, only the anti-pattern question of this table was analyzed. If other errors exist, these errors have been handled in other anti-patterns.

EVENT 1

Student Id: 4962	Total of submissions of the exercise:	9
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 4.7		

<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre>def main(): n=int(input()) i=1 while i<=n: a=int(input()) l=[] l.append(a)</pre> <p>Occurred in submission: 1 Observation: Each time you pass the line "l = []" all values of the array will be deleted.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <pre>def main(): n=int(input()) i=1 l=[] while i<=n: a=1 while a!=0: a=int(input()) l.append(a)</pre> <p>Fixed on submission: 6 Observation: The initialization of the array was placed out of repetition.</p>
EVENT 2	
<p>Student Id: 3498 Total of submissions of the exercise: 5</p> <p>The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 4.7</p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre>n=int(input()) c=raw_input() i=int i=1 while(i<=n): print ord(c[i])</pre> <p>Occurred in submission: 2 Observation: The reading of the value for "c" (2nd line) should be done within the "while" because it needs to repeat "n" times.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <pre>n=int(input()) i=int i=1 while(i<=n): c=raw_input() print ord(c) i=i+1</pre> <p>Fixed on submission: 5 Observation:</p>
EVENT 3	
<p>Student Id: 4674 Total of submissions of the exercise: 7</p> <p>The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 4.7</p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre>n=int(input()) x=raw_input() i=0 while i<n: print(x) i=i+1</pre> <p>Occurred in submission: 4 Observation: The reading of the value for "x" (2nd line) should be done within the "while" because it needs to repeat "n" times.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <pre>n=int(input()) i=0 while i<n: x=raw_input() print(x) i=i+1</pre> <p>Fixed on submission: 5 Observation:</p>
EVENT 4	
<p>Student Id: 5626 Total of submissions of the exercise: 11</p> <p>The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 8.1</p>	

Error

```
def determineSeOrdenado(n,vet):  
  
    for i in range(len(vet)):  
        ordem=False  
        if vet[i+1]>=vet[i]:  
            ordem=True  
        if ordem:  
            return 1  
        else:  
            return 0
```

Occurred in submission: 1

Observation: The command "ordem = False" should be before "for" and the structure "if order:" after.

Fixed Error

Fixed on submission:

Observation: The error has not been fixed.

A SUGGESTED SOLUTION

FOR PROFESSORS

Programming in front of the students, making the error appear – reinforce by asking students to develop new codes

FOR STUDENTS

Introduce the error into a code and understand the consequences it generates

ANTI-PATTERN GENERAL DATA

ID	TITLE				
P_SRS1	Use of repetition structure where selection should be				
EXAMPLE:					
<pre> a = int(input()) b = int(input()) c = int(input()) d = a + b + c st = "NAO" while d = 180: st = "SIM" d = 0 print(st , a , b , c) </pre>					
ERROR TYPE:		Syntax	X	Semantics	Style
CONTENT:		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Selection structure - Repetition structure 			
IN WHAT LANGUAGE WAS THE MISTAKE MADE?			C	X	Python
PROBLEM:					
Each structure has its purpose. Using repetition where only selection would be required will cause wrong results.					
CONNECTIONS TO OTHER ANTI-PATTERNS:					
EVENTS					
<p>Note: In the code snippets presented below, only the anti-pattern question of this table was analyzed. If other errors exist, these errors have been handled in other anti-patterns.</p>					
EVENT 1					
Student Id: 4890		Total of submissions of the exercise:			6
The exercise that was being solved:					
Exercise 3.1					
Error <pre> a = int(input()) b = int(input()) c = int(input()) d = a + b + c st = "NAO" while d = 180: st = "SIM" d = 0 print(st , a , b , c) </pre>			Fixed Error <div style="text-align: center; font-size: 2em; margin-top: 20px;">?</div>		
Occurred in submission: 1 Observation: Instead of the "while," it should be an "if."			Fixed on submission: Observation: The error has not been fixed.		
EVENT 2					

Student Id: 4914	Total of submissions of the exercise:	11
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The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 3.1		
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<p>Error</p> <pre style="font-family: monospace;">while a + b + c: print ("Sim" a, b, c) print ("NAO" a + b + c)</pre> <p>Occurred in submission: 5 Observation: Instead of the "while," it should be an "if."</p>	<p>Fixed Error</p> <pre style="font-family: monospace;">if a + b + c == 180: print ("Sim", a, b, c) else: print ("NAO", a + b + c)</pre> <p>Fixed on submission: 7 Observation:</p>
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EVENT 3		
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Student Id: 4970	Total of submissions of the exercise:	9
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The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 3.1		
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<p>Error</p> <pre style="font-family: monospace;">while a>0 and b>0 and c>0: if a + b + c == 180: print ("SIM") else: print ("NAO")</pre> <p>Occurred in submission: 1 Observation: "While" was used to verify that the values of "a", "b" and "c" are greater than 0 (zero). Although this check is not necessary for context, this check should have been used "if."</p>	<p>Fixed Error</p> <pre style="font-family: monospace;">if a>0 and b>0 and c>0: if a + b + c == 180: print ("SIM") else: print ("NAO")</pre> <p>Fixed on submission: 2 Observation:</p>
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EVENT 4		
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Student Id:	Total of submissions of the exercise:	
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The exercise that was being solved:		
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<p>Error</p> <p>Occurred in submission: Observation:</p>	<p>Fixed Error</p> <p>Fixed on submission: Observation:</p>
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A SUGGESTED SOLUTION		
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FOR PROFESSORS		
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Programming in front of the students, making the error appear – reinforce by asking students to develop new codes		
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FOR STUDENTS		
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Study one or more anti-patterns, introduce to classmate and reinforce with exercise		
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ANTI-PATTERN GENERAL DATA

ID	TITLE
P_MDA1	Wrong creation of multi-dimensional array lines

EXAMPLE:

```

m=int(input())
n=int(input())
linha=[]
A=[]
for i in range(m):
    for j in range(n):
        num=float(input())
        linha.append(num)

A.append(linha)
    
```


ERROR TYPE:	Syntax	X	Semantics			Style
CONTENT:	- Matrix: Creation					
IN WHAT LANGUAGE WAS THE MISTAKE MADE?		C		X		Python

PROBLEM:

Incorrectly creating an array row will cause the program to work improperly because the program will be incorrectly storing data.

CONNECTIONS TO OTHER ANTI-PATTERNS:

EVENTS

Note: In the code snippets presented below, only the anti-pattern question of this table was analyzed. If other errors exist, these errors have been handled in other anti-patterns.

EVENT 1

Student Id: 5538	Total of submissions of the exercise:	9
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The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 13.1

Error

```

m=int(input())
n=int(input())
linha=[]
A=[]
for i in range(m):
    for j in range(n):
        num=float(input())
        linha.append(num)

A.append(linha)
    
```

Fixed Error

```

m=int(input())
n=int(input())
linha=[]
A=[]
for i in range(m):
    for j in range(n):
        num=float(input())
        linha.append(num)

A.append(linha)
linha=[]
    
```

<p>Occurred in submission: 1 Observation: The line "linha= []" that creates the matrix line must be between the two "for" or repeated after "A.append (line)." As it stands, the second row will hold data from the first, the third from the second, and so on.</p>	<p>Fixed on submission: 9 Observation:</p>
EVENT 2	
<p>Student Id: 5714</p>	<p>Total of submissions of the exercise: 6</p>
<p>The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 13.1</p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre>def leitura(A): l=[] m=int(input()) n=int(input()) for i in range(m): for j in range(n): l.append(float(input())) A.append(l) return m,n</pre> <p>Occurred in submission: 1 Observation: The line "l = []" that creates the matrix line must be between the two "for" or to be repeated after "A.append (l)".</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <pre>def leitura(A): m=int(input()) n=int(input()) for i in range(m): l=[] for j in range(n): l.append(float(input())) A.append(l) return m,n</pre> <p>Fixed on submission: 6 Observation:</p>
EVENT 3	
<p>Student Id: 4946</p>	<p>Total of submissions of the exercise: 11</p>
<p>The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 13.1</p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre>def CriaMatriz(matriz, m, n): linha = [] for i in range(m): for j in range(n): x = float(input()) linha.append(x) matriz.append(linha) return(matriz)</pre> <p>Occurred in submission: 1 Observation: The line "l = []" that creates the matrix line must be between the two "for" or to be repeated after "matriz.append(linha)."</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <pre>def CriaMatriz(matriz, m, n): linha = [] for i in range(m): linha = [] for j in range(n): x = float(input()) linha.append(x) matriz.append(linha) #print(matriz) #print(matriz) return(matriz)</pre> <p>Fixed on submission: 10 Observation:</p>
EVENT 4	
<p>Student Id:</p>	<p>Total of submissions of the exercise:</p>
<p>The exercise that was being solved:</p>	

Error	Fixed Error
Occurred in submission: Observation:	Fixed on submission: Observation:
A SUGGESTED SOLUTION	
FOR PROFESSORS	
Apply the bench test (table test) in code samples with and without the error, compare the results – reinforce by asking the students to solve some exercises	
FOR STUDENTS	
Study one or more anti-patterns, introduce to classmate and reinforce with exercise	

ANTI-PATTERN GENERAL DATA

ID	TITLE
P_F8	Function created but not called

EXAMPLE:

```
def main():
    n = int(input())
    print(n)
```

ERROR TYPE:	<input type="checkbox"/> Syntax	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Semantics	<input type="checkbox"/> Style
CONTENT:	- Function: Call		
IN WHAT LANGUAGE WAS THE MISTAKE MADE?	<input type="checkbox"/> C	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Python	

PROBLEM:

With the creation of a function, it is assumed that it is necessary for the correct operation of the program. Creating it but not calling it will cause that any task that the program needs to perform will not be executed.

CONNECTIONS TO OTHER ANTI-PATTERNS:

EVENTS

Note: In the code snippets presented below, only the anti-pattern question of this table was analyzed. If other errors exist, these errors have been handled in other anti-patterns.

EVENT 1

Student Id: 4826	Total of submissions of the exercise:	4
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 1.1		
<p>Error</p> <pre>def main(): n = int(input()) print(n)</pre> <p>Occurred in submission: 3 Observation: The "main" function was created but not called.</p>	<p>Fixed Error</p> <pre>def main(): n = int(input()) print(n) main()</pre> <p>Fixed on submission: 4 Observation:</p>	

EVENT 2

Student Id: 4842	Total of submissions of the exercise:	4
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 1.1		
<p>Error</p>	<p>Fixed Error</p>	

<pre>def main(): n=int.input() print(n)</pre> <p>Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:</p>	<pre>def main(): n=int.input() print(n) main()</pre> <p>Fixed on submission: 2 Observation:</p>
EVENT 3	
<p>Student Id: 4850 Total of submissions of the exercise: 3</p>	
<p>The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 2.1</p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre>def main(): a=int(input()) b=int(input()) if a>b: print(a) else: print(b)</pre> <p>Occurred in submission: 2 Observation:</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <pre>def main(): a=int(input()) b=int(input()) if a>b: print(a) else: print(b) main()</pre> <p>Fixed on submission: 3 Observation:</p>
EVENT 4	
<p>Student Id: 4674 Total of submissions of the exercise: 3</p>	
<p>The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 2.1</p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre>def main(): i=int(input()) j=i*i print(j)</pre> <p>Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <pre>def main(): i=int(input()) j=i*i print(j) main()</pre> <p>Fixed on submission: 2 Observation:</p>
A SUGGESTED SOLUTION	
FOR PROFESSORS	
<p>Programming in front of the students, making the error appear – reinforce by asking students to develop new codes</p>	
FOR STUDENTS	
<p>Study one or more anti-patterns, introduce to classmate and reinforce with exercise</p>	